

Competence and Challenges Encountered by Research Enthusiasts in Infanta District: Basis for Research Capacity Building

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ABSTRACT

Every teacher has struggled with how to conduct an action research since doing one requires the right abilities and extra time to plan and complete it. As a result, few teachers engage in action research. To dive into this issue, the researcher attempted to conduct a research investigation with a focus on the competence and challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an action research in Infanta District of School Year 2022-2023. The aim of this research was also to propose a research capacity building. The researcher used purposive sampling, employing descriptive-quantitative method. The results revealed that the research enthusiasts assessed their competence as "Slightly Competent" as reflected by the overall mean of 2.14. Meanwhile, one item was evaluated where the research enthusiast was "not competent" which this is about making an introduction using CARS Model. On the other hand, the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts were interpreted as "Slightly Serious" with an overall weighted mean of 2.53. While, four problems were identified as "Serious" such as they do not know the difference between an action research and basic research, they need individuals who can guide them in making their research paper, someone who can give them Technical Assistance and they do not have a background in the process of making an action research. Moreover, two "Very Serious" challenges were found such as they do not have training in Action Research and due to this lack of training, it made them reluctant in doing one. In the meantime, the computed coefficient or r value was .56 which signified a considerable moderate correlation. Therefore, the research enthusiasts' competence registered a relationship with the challenges they encountered. To address the serious and very serious problems encountered, the research enthusiasts may find the research capacity building proposed in this paper. The capacity building is purposely

designed to resolve and overcome the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in making an action research.

INTRODUCTION

Individuals who are engaged in the task of education have to face many such problems which hinder the education of children. Thus, teachers need to find out solutions of such problems on the basis of their own investigation as this process will immediately point out to remedial measures to be adopted. In this regard, one of scientific methods that can be used in addressing the said problems is through a research-based plans and solutions that should be implemented in schools. (Jha, 2022)

Moreover, as stipulated in DO 16, s.2017 otherwise known as the Research Management Guidelines (RMG) that supports the department's policy development process, research agenda, and program development and implementation, the Department of Education (DepEd) continues to support and strengthen the culture of research in basic education.

Having said that, Bongcayao (2023), stressed that teachers as frontliners of basic education may conduct an Action Research to assess their teaching practices, reflect on learning outcomes, and generate practical ways of improving their pedagogical competence through innovations and interventions that will result in positive educational impact and school effectiveness. Meanwhile, it is also presented that still many teachers are experiencing difficulties in the conduct of action research from the identification of their research problem until the publication of the results of the research. The results may imply that teachers do not yet possess the required skills in writing action researches.

However, Tindowen (2019) conducted a study regarding the conception and difficulties experienced by teachers in conducting an action research and found out that still many teachers are experiencing difficulties in the conduct of action research from the identification of their research problem until the publication of the results of the research. The results may imply that teachers do not yet possess the required skills in writing action researches.

Moreover, according to Bullo, et.al. (2021), conducting educational research has become one of the most challenging tasks to most of the teachers, especially because it has been an additional work to them. Their study revealed that most of respondents encountered challenges in conducting research like the lack of time, have anxieties in writing and conducting the study and perceived research as an additional burden on their part.

These issues pushed the researcher to conduct a research investigation aimed at identifying the competence and challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an Action Research for School Year 2022-2023 as a basis in proposing a research capability building.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research aimed to determine the competence and the problems encountered by the research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon as a basis in formulating a research capacity building. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the level of the competence among research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon in conducting an Action Research?
2. What are the problems encountered by the research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon in conducting an Action Research?
3. Is there a significant relationship to the competence and the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon in conducting an Action Research?
4. Based on the findings of this research, what research capacity building program may be designed for the research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon?

METHODOLOGY

This research was delimited to all research coordinators and enthusiasts in Infanta District in the Division of Quezon for School Year 2022-2023. Its main concern was to determine and analyze competence and challenges encountered by the said research enthusiasts as a basis for proposing a research capacity building. Meanwhile, quantitative research that employed a descriptive research design was used in this research.

Research Design

This research investigation utilized Quantitative Research that employed a descriptive research design since the competence and challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an action research were measured and evaluated quantitatively.

Sampling

Purposive sampling was used since the researcher utilized some criteria for the respondents such as the respondents otherwise known as the research enthusiasts may be a research coordinator or a teacher who is passionate to conduct an action research in Infanta District. Also, an enthusiast had to be willing enough to train in the four-day proposed research capacity building. Thus, this research investigation involved 39 research enthusiasts who served as the research respondents.

Instrumentation and Validation

The instrument used was a researcher-made survey questionnaire. It was designed to measure the competence and the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an Action Research for School Year 2022-2023. The said instrument is consists of two parts: the first part measures the research enthusiasts' competence (10

items) and the second part deals with the challenges they encountered in conducting an Action Research.

To contextualize the survey instrument and to validate the content/ items, a dry run was conducted. This dry-run was conducted from the same district which involved twenty (20) research enthusiasts who were not part of the study. The researcher asked the permission to conduct the said dry-run to the district supervisor through a letter. The data gathered from the dry-run was subjected to a statistic Cronbach's Alpha to determine its reliability. The computed coefficient which was 0.81 confirmed that the survey instrument was good and valid.

Statistical tools

In order to interpret and analyze the data collected from the respondents, the following statistical tools were used:

1. This was used in analyzing the level of the competence and the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an Action Research. This method was used to calculate the average value of the data by providing different weights to some of the individual values.
2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r). This was used in determining the relationship between the research enthusiasts' competence and the challenges they encountered. This Pearson r finds the degree of association of two sets of variables.
3. Cronbach's alpha. This was used to validate the survey questionnaire and to measure the internal consistency of a set of items, or how closely connected they are to one another as a group. It can be expressed in terms of the quantity of test items and their average intercorrelation.

To interpret the results of the research enthusiasts' competence in conducting an action research, the scale below was used:

3.26-4.00	Highly Competent
2.51-3.25	Competent
1.76-2.50	Slightly Competent
1.00-1.75	Not Competent

Meanwhile, to interpret the challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts in conducting an action research, the scale below was used:

3.26-4.00	Challenge is Very Serious
2.51-3.25	Challenge is Serious
1.76-2.50	Challenge is Slightly Serious
1.00-1.75	Not a Challenge At All

RESULTS

This chapter covers the results and discussion concerning the competence and challenges encountered by research enthusiasts in conducting an action research. The order of the discussion follows the arrangement of the Statement of the Problem in Chapter 1.

Specific Question No.1 What is the level of the competence among research coordinators in Infanta, Quezon in conducting an Action Research?

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1	I know how to make a research introduction using CARS Model.	1.62	Not Competent	10
2	I can construct Statement of the Problem (SOP) logically.	2.33	Slightly Competent	2
3	I am able to efficiently write Review of Related Literature and Studies.	3.11	Competent	1
4	I know the different Research Designs in making an Action Research.	2.18	Slightly Competent	4.5
5	I know how to make a sampling from the total population.	1.92	Slightly Competent	7
6	I can interpret the data gathered with supporting Related Literature and Studies.	1.88	Slightly Competent	8
7	I can systematically generate conclusions based on the given findings.	1.81	Slightly Competent	9
8	I can generate recommendations based on the given findings and conclusions.	2.11	Slightly Competent	6
9	I know how to facilitate research dissemination and utilization.	2.28	Slightly Competent	3
10	I know the research ethics very well.	2.18	Slightly Competent	4.5
	Average Weighted Mean	2.14	Slightly Competent	

Table 1 presents the weighted means, verbal interpretations and ranks on the competence of research enthusiasts in conducting an action research for School Year 2022-2023. As shown above, one out ten categories had a verbal interpretation as ‘Competent’. “I am able to efficiently write Review of Related Literature and Studies” ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 3.11.

On the other hand, 8 out of ten categories had a verbal interpretation of “Slightly Competent”. “I can construct Statement of the Problem (SOP) logically” ranked 2 with a

weighted mean of 2.33. Having a weighted mean of 2.28 is “I know how to facilitate research dissemination and utilization” ranked 3. “I know the different Research Designs in making an Action Research” and “I know the research ethics very well” both ranked 4.5 with a weighted mean of 2.18. “I can generate recommendations based on the given findings and conclusions” ranked 6 with a weighted mean of 2.11. Ranked 7 is “I know how to make a sampling from the total population” with a weighted mean of 1.92 . Ranked 8 and 9 is “I can interpret the data gathered with supporting Related Literature and Studies” and “I can systematically generate conclusions based on the given findings” had weighted means of 1.88 and 1.81 respectively.

While, one item out of ten had a verbal interpretation of “Not Competent” which is “I know how to make a research introduction using CARS Model” ranked 10 with a weighted mean of 1.62. As disclosed, only one item had a verbal interpretation of “competent”. While the rest of the items were verbally interpreted as “Slightly Competent” and one had “Not Competent” having an average weighted mean of 2.14 with was verbally interpreted as “Slightly Competent”. The results of the data speak that research enthusiasts need to be equipped with trainings and capacity building as to develop and enrich their competence in making an action research.

The findings of the study is supported by Oestar and Marzo, (2022) who conducted an investigation on the impact of capacity building and trainings to improve the ability of teachers. Their findings revealed that competencies with low ratings should be mastered through capability-building activities. Some of the barriers that hinder the engagement of teachers in action research making were the knowledge, attitude, and resource factors. To remedy such issues and corners, it can be recommended that teachers may personally attend additional training and workshops that focus on the importance and benefits of action research and enhance competencies.

Specific Question No. 2 What is the level of the competence among research coordinators in Infanta, Quezon in conducting an Action Research?

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1	I do not have enough training in making an Action Research.	3.42	Challenge is Very Serious	1
2	Lack of training in making an Action Research makes me reluctant in doing one.	3.31	Challenge is Very Serious	2
3	I do not know the difference between an Action Research and Basic Research.	2.85	Challenge is Serious	5
4	I need someone who can coach/give me technical assistance in making my research paper.	3.14	Challenge is Serious	4

5	I cannot find time in making an action research because of so many ancillaries in school.	1.68	Not A Challenge at All	8.5
6	Conducting an Action Research is not actually my forte.	1.72	Not A Challenge at All	7
7	I cannot give Technical Assistance to my colleagues even if I am their research.	2.79	Challenge is Serious	6
8	I do not have a background regarding the process of making an Action Research.	3.17	Challenge is Serious	3
9	I do not have the resources to complete my research paper.	1.68	Not A Challenge At All	8.5
10	I am hesitant to conduct an Action Research because I might receive a lot of Technical Assistance once I submit my paper.	1.56	Not A Challenge at All	10
	Average Weighted Mean	2.53	Challenge is Slightly Serious	

Table 2 presents the weighted means, verbal interpretations and ranks on the challenges encountered by research enthusiasts in conducting an action research for School Year 2020-2021. As shown above, 2 out of 10 items had verbal interpretation as “Challenge is Very Serious” . “I do not have enough training in making an Action Research” ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 3.42, while “Lack of training in making an Action Research makes me reluctant in doing one” ranked 2 with a weighted mean of 3.31.

Meanwhile, 4 out of 10 items had a verbal interpretation of “Challenge is Serious”. “I do not have a background regarding the process of making an Action Research” ranked 3 with a weighted mean of 3.17. Ranked 4 with a weighted mean of 3.14 is “I need someone who can coach/give me technical assistance in making my research paper”. Ranked 5 is “I do not know the difference between an Action Research and Basic Research” with weighted mean of 2.85. Ranked 6 is “I cannot give Technical Assistance to my colleagues even if I am their research’ with a weighted mean of 2.79.

On the other hand, 4 items had a verbal interpretation of “Not A Problem At All”. “Conducting an Action Research is not actually my forte” ranked 7 with a weighted mean of 1.72. “ I cannot find time in making an action research because of so many ancillaries in school” and “I do not have the resources to complete my research paper” both ranked 8.5 and had a weighted mean of 1.68 while “I am hesitant to conduct an Action Research because I might receive a lot of Technical Assistance once I submit my paper” ranked 10 with a weighted mean of 1.56.

The challenges encountered of the research enthusiasts had an average weighted mean of 2.53 and verbally interpreted as “Challenge is Slightly Serious”. As disclosed, although there are items that fall under “Challenge is Slightly Serious”, there are also items under “Challenge is Very Serious” and “Challenge is Serious” which denote that there are some factors to be considered as to help the research enthusiasts with the challenges they encountered in conducting an action research

The findings of the study is supported by Abrenica and Cascolan (2022) who found out that Action research, according to the teachers, has a positive impact in the teaching-learning process. However, there are challenges that need to be addressed in conducting an action research. While Alipio (2019) stressed that since teachers encountered problems in conducting in action research, they need to participate to various division initiative. He concluded that research activities such as capacity building and trainings. Likewise, through capacity building, the challenges of the teachers in conducting an action research can be addressed as it had greatly improved the research skills of the respondents.

Specific Question No.3 Is there a significant relationship to the research enthusiasts’ competence and the challenges they encountered?

**Table 3
Correlations between Competence and Challenges Encountered by the Research Enthusiasts**

Scores Paired	Coefficient of Correlation	Level of Significance	Interpretation	Decision
Research Enthusiats’ Competence Vs Challenges Encountered	0.56	0.05	With Significant Relationship	Reject Ho

Scale: Range of Values

± 0.90 – 1.00 Very high correlation; very dependable relationship

± 0.70 – 0.89 High correlation; marked relationship

± 0.40 – 0.69 Moderate correlation; substantial relationship

± 0.20 – 0.39 Low correlation; definite but small relationship

Less than ± 0.20 Negligible correlation

The computed coefficient correlation or r-value was 0.56 which signified a considerable moderate correlation. Therefore, the research enthusiasts’ competence registered a relationship with the challenges they encountered.

Hence, the findings rejected the null hypothesis. This only means that there is a significant relationship between the research enthusiasts' competence with the challenges they encountered in conducting an action research.

Specific Question No. 4. Based on the findings of this research, what research capacity building program may be designed for the research enthusiasts in Infanta, Quezon?

The Proposed Research Capacity Building

Theme: District Capacity Building for Teachers in Combatting Learning Loss Through Action Research

I. RATIONALE

The global CoVid-19 pandemic has caused an unprecedented change in all walks of life. It has clutched different sectors and overthrown people around the world to a new social and economic crisis. Unfortunately, education is one of the fields affected since around 1.52 billion students remain out of school and over 60.2 million teachers are stranded at home. (UN Secretary General as cited by Sarif, 2020). Having said that, according to Domingue (2021), there is a grave concern about "learning loss" among learners given the scope of the COVID-19 pandemic disruptions. He further said that "learning loss" refers to the discrepancy between a student's real abilities after the disruptions caused by COVID-19 and the abilities the student would have developed in the context of conventional educational practice. Likewise, he said that if nothing is done, the pandemic's effects on pupils' learning development will likely have a long-term negative effect. Nevertheless, he asserted that this issue may still be resolved by figuring out what is taking place in specific schools so that practical solutions can be widely disseminated. Thus, it can be argued that seminars, trainings, and workshops must be organized so that teachers would be trained and competent to create their own interventions in order to prevent the learners' learning loss.

In line with this, the Infanta District Research Committee will organize a seminar-workshop to enrich the teachers' knowledge and action research skills in response to the learning loss brought by the COVID-19 pandemic.

II. OBJECTIVES

After the four-day training-workshop, teachers are expected to:

1. Acquire new knowledge and skills in making their own action research
2. Develop a Complete Action Research.

III. PARTICIPANTS

PSDS
District Research Committee
Techers

IV. DATE AND VENUE

The date will be determined after the approval of this proposed Research Capacity Building
ICES Social Hall
Infanta, Quezon

V. EXPECTED OUTPUT

1. Complete Action Research
2. Newly designed interventions to combat the learning loss among learners.

VI. BUDGETARY REQUIREMENTS

Expenses to be incurred in this seminar will be charged against LGU's Special Education Fund which is subject to the usual auditing procedures.

VII. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The Public Schools District Supervisor together with the District Research Committee will conduct the monitoring and evaluation to ensure proper utilization of funds, precise management and effectiveness of the training.

Prepared and Managed by:
RAMIL A. BORREO, EdD
Master Teacher I/Organizer

Training Matrix

Date	Topic/s
Day 1	Organizing Research Introduction
Day 2	Gathering Related Literature and Studies
Day 3	Formulating Research Methodology
Day 4	Interpreting the Research Findings and Supplying Discussions (Chapter 4) Drawing Conclusions and Recommendations (Chapter 5)

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions had been derived:

1. The research enthusiasts are just marginally competent in conducting an action research.
2. The challenges encountered by the research enthusiasts were slightly bearable. However, some challenges were serious and very serious like they don't have enough

trainings in conducting an action research, and needed individuals who will guide them in doing it.

3. The competence of the research enthusiasts registered a relationship with the challenges they encountered. Hence, the findings rejected the null hypothesis. Therefore, one can determine that since research enthusiasts feel that they lack in terms of their research competence, there will be some challenges that they will encounter in making an action research.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The Public Schools District Supervisor needs to:

a. Plan and implement more research programs such as trainings/capacity building to capacitate the research enthusiasts and equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge in making an action research by adopting and utilizing the research capacity building proposed in this research paper.

b. Facilitate and conduct monitoring and evaluation together with the District Research Committee every month to the school research coordinators and research enthusiasts and assist them through giving of Technical Assistance.

2. The School Heads may consider to:

a. Encourage and help the teachers in attending research trainings initiated and facilitated by the Department of Education and other private organizations to develop their research competence by aiding them on their financial needs by including the said trainings to the Annual Implementation Plan (AIP) and other means and ways whether it may be from Canteen Funds, donations, etc.

3. The Research Enthusiasts need to:

a. Attend and participate to research trainings/capacity building from the district, division, regional, national and international level to improve their research competence.

b. Establish a well-planned and systematic Research Plan/Timeline as to give research directions and to monitor their research paper's progress.

c. Initiate a dialogue to the District Research Committee for them to be given assistance on their research paper.

4. To the Future Researchers

a. Conduct an in-depth investigation on the possible impact of Research Capacity Building/trainings in developing the teacher's competence in making an action research.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

The researcher sought an approval first from the Public Schools District Supervisor stating the areas and data he needed with a permission from the participants before answering the questionnaire. Meanwhile, the researcher guaranteed that all the answers and responses of the teacher-respondents have remained confidential since the researchers did not name or involved their names, nor the institution they were in to secure their confidentiality and anonymity.

REFERENCES

- Abrenica, J. and Cascolan, H. (2022), Impact of action research in education: experiences and challenges faced by teachers. https://ijsmr.in/doc/ijsmr05_13.pdf
- Albalawi, A. and Johnson, LN. (2022). Action research skills among public school teachers: A cross-cultural study <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1346963.pdf>
- Alipio, J. (2019). Improving the research skills of teachers through revitalized research and development program. <https://depedro1.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/John-Silvester-Alipio.pdf>
- Azarcon, D. (2019), Challenges encountered by master teachers in conducting action research. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/5909>
- Bongcayao, A. (2023). Capacitating teachers' research skills through collaborative action research buddies. <https://ijmaberjournal.org/index.php/ijmaber/article/view/970>
- Bullo, M. et.al. (2021), Challenges and difficulties encountered by teachers in the conduct of educational research: Basis for teachers' enhancement program. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353803414_Challenges_and_difficulties_encountered_by_teachers_in_the_conduct_of_educational_research_Basis_for_teachers'_enhancement_program
- De Borja, A. (2018). Teacher action research: its difficulties and implications. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/268003940>
- Caingcoy, M. (2020). Research capability of teachers: its correlates, determinants and implication for continuing professional development <file:///C:/Users/vincentjace/Downloads/SSRN-id3631867.pdf>
- Jha, R. (2022). Importance of action research in education. <https://www.inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/983967279.pdf>
- Oestar J. and Marzo, C. (2022). Teachers as researchers: Skills and challenges in action research making https://www.researchgate.net/profile/JenniferOestar/publication/364954616_Teachers_as_Researchers_Skills_and_Challenges_in_Action_Research_Making/links/636097196e0d367d91e5656f/Teachers-as-Researchers-Skills-and-Challenges-in-Action-Research-Making.pdf
- Rommelspacher, A. (2020). How to structure your literature review. <https://gradcoach.com/literature-review-structure/>
- Sarif, N. (2020). Teaching crisis and teachers' role in times of CoVid-19 pandemic. <https://countercurrents.org/2020/08/teaching-crisis-and-teachers-role-in-times-of-covid-19-pandemic/>

- Tindowen, D. (2019). Teachers' conception and difficulties in doing action research.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334963031_Teachers'_Conception_and_Difficulties_in_Doing_Action_Research
- Tingabngab, V. and Binayao, B. (2023). Challenges faced by the public elementary school teachers in conducting action research
<file:///C:/Users/vincentjace/Downloads/10.11648.j.tecs.20230801.13.pdf>